

An IEEE 754 Double-Precision Floating-Point Multiplier for Denormalized and Normalized Floating-Point Numbers

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Abstract—This paper discusses an optimized double-precision floating-point multiplier that can handle both denormalized and normalized IEEE 754 floating-point numbers. Discussions of the optimizations are given and compared versus similar implementations, however, the main objective is keeping compliant for denormalized IEEE 754 floating-point numbers while still maintaining high performance operations for normalized numbers.

I. PAPER

Although multiplication is straight-forward to implement, there is still a need to preserve precision for denormal numbers. One particular method to handle denormalized IEEE-754 numbers uses injection-based rounding within its architecture [1]. While this technique in [1] is helpful for denormalized numbers, it does not completely address denormal operands and outputs with correct rounding within the IEEE 754 standard. The major contribution of this paper is that it utilizes the injection-based rounding for multiplication and applies it correctly to IEEE 754 normalized and denormalized numbers.

A. Multiplier Design I

The first design produces a fully compliant IEEE 754 double precision binary floating-point multiplier that is primarily designed around an injection-based rounding algorithm [1]. To further improve the design additional hardware is added to fully support denormal operands and results. After partial product reduction, the carry save pair is added with the injection constant using a row of carry save adders and a carry propagate adder. Concurrently, rounding is computed using the Even and Seidel (ES) fixed position injection based algorithm [1].

The Even/Seidel rounding algorithm (ES), as shown in Figure 1, works by reducing the four rounding modes (RM); round to zero (RZ), round to nearest even (RNE), round up (RPI), and round down (RNI) to a single truncation operation [1]. The process has two steps: first, RPI and RNI are reduced into one of two modes, either RZ or a new mode round to infinity (RI) using the product's sign bit and the direction of the rounding. When the sign matches the rounding direction, RPI and positive, or RNI and negative the rounding mode is RI, otherwise RZ. Second, an injection constant is added to the

intermediate product, such that all modes reduce to truncation at the rounding bit position. The injection constant (INJ) is defined as:

$$INJ = \begin{cases} 0 & : RZ \\ 2^{-53} & : RNE \\ 2^{-52} - 2^{-104} & : RI \end{cases}$$

This only works when the product is in the range $[1, 2)$, but the mantissa can overflow into the range $[2, 4)$ requiring a injection correction (INJCOR) to be added into the product. The ES algorithm provides little advice about computing the sticky, round, and *carry*[0] bits. Finding *round* and *carry*[0] requires computing the carry propagate chain through all bits in the lower path, -1 to -52 , however, only the sum bit needs be generated at bit -1 . Using a technique from [2], the sticky can be computed directly from the carry save format.

To account for *carry*[0] carrying into the upper data path and the INJCOR, the technique in the ES paper uses a special increment decision, *Tinc* (INC in the ES paper). The equation definition in the ES paper is correct, however, we believe there is a small mistake in the implementation logic within [1]. *Tinc* should increment when the majority of round (*R*), *carry*[0] (*C*), and *Lx* are high and the mantissa has overflowed $Y0[52] = 1$ and the rounding mode is RNE. In the case of $Lx = 1$, $R = 1$, and $C = 0$, the logic incorrectly sets $Tinc = 0$. The following equation correctly implements *Tinc*.

$$Tinc = \begin{cases} (C \cdot R \cdot RNE) + (L \cdot R \cdot RNE) \\ + ((L + C) \cdot RI) \\ + (C \cdot L \cdot (RZ + RNE)) & : \overline{Y0[53]} \\ L \cdot C & : Y0[53] \end{cases}$$

Finally, to support a second stage of rounding and the inexact flag, *Tinx* is computed so that it indicates if the current rounding is not the infinitely precise answer.

$$Tinx = \begin{cases} R + S & : RZ \cdot \overline{Y0[53]} \\ R + S + (Lx \oplus C[52]) & : RZ \cdot Y0[53] \\ \overline{R} + S & : (RI + RNE) \cdot \overline{Y0[53]} \\ \overline{R} + S + (Lx \oplus C[52]) & : (RI + RNE) \cdot Y0[53] \end{cases}$$

When the exponent is less than e_{min} (0), the product is no longer a valid IEEE 754 number. To correct this problem the

Fig. 1: Details of the first step of the rounding hardware. This follows the design of Even and Seidel, but generates signal T_{inx} for the second stage of rounding. Also, the 106 bit sum is segmented into two carry/save parts [53:0] and [-1:-52].

Fig. 2: Block diagram of the mantissa path when shifting the carry save redundant from before adding the injection constant. Note: the barrel shifters in the packing and unpacking modules have been removed.

mantissa is shifted right such that the exponent is increased to $emin$. However, this presents a problem for the rounding function as the rounding position has now moved resulting in incorrectly rounded product. By applying multistep gradual rounding, a second stage of rounding ensures the proper position is rounded [3]. Additionally the input to the ES method requires the inputs be normalized. Denormal operands are detected using a leading zero counter and then shifted to normalize. This adds delay to the critical path which will be reduced in the next section.

B. Multiplier Design II: Fast Denormal Rounding

Multistep gradual rounding is expensive in terms of delay and area as the sticky bit must be computed twice and an extra +1 adder is needed. To work around the issue, the injection based rounding has to be modified to support adding the injection at variable positions. A better solution uses a fixed injection constant, but shifts the intermediate product such that the round bit aligns to the injection constant before adding. This is achieved by moving the barrel shifter from the final packing circuit and inserting it between the partial product reduction and final carry-propagate addition. Shifting the carry/save intermediate product effectively does two things: first, it normalizes the mantissa in the event of an exponent below $emin$ and second, it aligns the mantissa to the correct rounding position.

In the previous multiplier, the packing (denormalizing) shifter needed to shift up to 54 bits to completely underflow a result. Because the shift now occurs prior to overflow detection (mantissa [2,4]) the shifter will need a maximum shift of 55.

An additional optimization can be made now that the shifting occurs before adding the carry-save intermediate product. In the original ES method, the mantissas need to be normalized to ensure the rounding position is known. Moreover, this new method eliminates that requirement. The unpacking pre-normalization step can be removed if the shifter is modified to shift in both directions. Doing so, dramatically reduces the unpacking delay by eliminating a shifter and removing the leading zero detection from the critical path.

C. Conclusion

Two multipliers have been implemented in RTL-based Verilog and verified for compliance with the IEEE 754 standard. Both versions, the multistep and fast architectures, have been fully verified against SoftFloat [4]. Both designs are based upon the fixed position injection constant rounding method presented by Even and Seidel, but extend their work to provide support for rounding denormal numbers [1].

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